

ISic2878

I.Sicily inscription 2878

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrillae

Place of origin (modern)

Chiaramonte Gulfi

Provenance

contrada San Nicolo Giglia, between Chiaramonte and Comiso

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Kamarina, Museo Archeologico
Regionale di Kamarina, inventory 5985

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI178079

1. Ἰάσων
2. τὸ νήπι-
3. ον.
4. ²menorah²
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645272

EDCS 38000218

PHI 178079

Bibliography

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